

Sheep Grazing in Olive Groves: Challenges and Opportunities

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Olive grove with extensive grazing with Churra Badana sheep

Traditionally, throughout their history, olive groves have been grazed by sheep. It was with the specialization of agriculture, the introduction of mechanical means, the use of chemical fertilizers and plant protection products that a profound transformation in the management of olive groves began. The reintroduction of the practice of managing the vegetation of the understory (spontaneous or clippings) by grazing as an alternative to the use of herbicides or ploughing is now seen as a modern and innovative approach. The potential benefits of grazing olive groves with sheep include a reduction in the cost of eliminating unwanted vegetation, a reduction in the use of machinery and the consumption of fossil fuels, an improvement in soil fertility through the contribution of droppings and the recycling of nutrients, an improvement in soil structure and biodiversity. Also, the consumption of fallen fruit and leaves (potential carriers of pests and olive disease inoculums) can reduce the need for phytosanitary treatments. In addition, the olive grove's food resources - herbaceous vegetation and pruned leaves - are valorised. The leaves improve the quality of the milk due to their high linoleic acid content and have a positive effect on the fatty acid profile of the cheese. When planning grazing, in addition to the need to adjust the animal load (number of animals/ha) to the availability of food resources, aspects linked to the animal's anatomy and behaviour should be taken into account (favouring smaller, more sedentary animals), thus avoiding access to and consumption of tree leaves, as well as the season and grazing system.

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